

ELECTROLYSIS OF REGOLITH SIMULANT FOR SIMULTANEOUS OXYGEN AND METAL PRODUCTION.

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Introduction: Worldwide, spatial agencies agree that future missions of exploration on the Moon will require longer stay for activities on the lunar surface than in Apollo missions, implying for these long-duration missions to settle down soon with permanent lunar bases to sustain technical and scientific activities, with the future perspective of a human settlement on Mars. In this context, incorporation of In-Situ Resources Utilization (ISRU) to produce life support consumables and everyday life objects will greatly reduce the mass, the cost and the risk of missions and will lead to expand the human being exploration efforts on the Moon. The ISRU concept considers the resources at the exploration site with the use of lunar regolith (rocks, soils) as a raw material, with the following objectives: extraction of breathing oxygen, - water production and - formation of metals (as feedstocks for in-situ manufacturing).

Objectives: Our objective is to propose an autonomous improved electrochemical process to be implemented on various Moon sites selected to take advantage of significant regolith presence to simultaneously produce metals and oxygen.

Ongoingwork: in this context, the behaviour of a lunar soil analog was investigated in LiF-NaF at 800°C for in situ production by electrolysis of metals (cathode) and O₂ gas (anode) as a part of In Situ Resource Utilization (ISRU) research. It is based on regolith simulant dissolution in a LiF-NaF molten fluoride solvent at 800°C, leading to metallic cations and oxide anions, which were then reduced into metal and oxidised into O₂ respectively by electrolysis. A basalt-type rock from the Pic d'Ysson site, called Basalt Pic d'Ysson Naturel (BPY-N), which has been extensively characterized in many respects was used as an analogue of lunar regolith [1, 2].

The 1st step was to compare the individual solubility of the main oxides composing the lunar soil (SiO₂, Al₂O₃, Fe₂O₃, FeTiO₃ and MgO) with the solubility of the crystalline analog using Inductively Coupled Plasma – Atomic Emission Spectroscopy.

The 2nd step was to verify by cyclic voltammetry the electroactivity of all oxide species in LiF-NaF. Electrolyses on different cathodic substrates were performed at different conditions and analysed with a scanning electron microscope (SEM-EDS). Then, the electrochemical behaviour of the crystalline lunar simulant was compared with a mixed powder made of the different oxides [3].

The last step is the oxygen extraction from the lunar soil, where the need of resistant materials used under severe conditions is essential. Electrochemical studies and oxygen gas analyser were used to demonstrate and quantify the amount of produced O₂. The outputs are very promising and will be discussed.

References:

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